

Synthesis of Azasteroids with Pyrazoline and Isoxazoline Rings

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17-Oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate (1) on reaction with dimethyl oxalate afforded the glyoxalate, 16-carbomethoxycarbonyl-17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate (2) which on reaction with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine and hydroxyl amine hydrochloride gave the corresponding 3 β -acetoxy-5'-carbomethoxyandrost-5-en [17, 16-c] pyrazole (3). 3 β -acetoxy-5'-carbomethoxy-1'-phenylandrost-5-en [17, 16-c] pyrazole (4) and 3 β -acetoxy-3'-carbomethoxyandrost-5-en [17, 16-c] isoxazole (5).

The steroidal compounds with fused pyrazole ring¹ and fused isoxazole ring² systems possess various biological activities.

Earlier, the Claisen condensation of steroidal ketones with dimethyl oxalate have been reported by Ruzicka and Platner³, Ramadas and Kumar⁴ in total synthesis of steroids, Fravolini and coworkers⁵ and Merck company⁶ the glyoxalate (2) intermediate was utilised for synthesis of pyrazoles and isoxazole derivatives. In continuation of our earlier work⁷, we report here the synthesis of steroidal pyrazole and isoxazole derivatives by Claisen condensation of steroidal ketone, 17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate using dimethyl oxalate.

The oxalation reaction of 17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate (1) using dimethyl oxalate in the presence of sodium methoxide in an atmosphere of nitrogen afforded the glyoxalate, 16-carbomethoxycarbonyl-17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate (2). The glyoxalate (2) may exist in two tautomeric forms (2a and 2b). The structure 2a is more stable due to greater hydrogen bonding. The spectral data indicate tautomer 2a being more plausible.

The reaction of the glyoxalate (2) with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid solution furnished the pyrazole derivative (3), which may exist in either tautomeric form 3a or 3b. The tautomeric forms 3a is more plausible as the glyoxalate exists preferably as tautomer 2a, and it will also be stabilised in hydrogen bonding between NH proton and C=O of carbomethoxy group. The ir and nmr spectral data suggest that structure 3a is valid.

The glyoxalate (2) on reaction with phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride in acetic acid solution in the presence of sodium acetate afforded the phenyl pyrazole derivative (4), which may also exist as isomers 4a and 4b. However on analogy with the other pyrazole (3a) and from the spectral data, the isomer 4a is preferable.

The glyoxalate (2) on reaction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acetic acid solution in the presence of sodium acetate provided isoxazole derivative (5) which may also exist as isomers 5a and 5b. The isomer 5a which is derived from tautomer 2a of

the glyoxalate is more plausible the spectral data are in agreement with the preferable formation of the pyrazoles 3a and 4a.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (95% ethanol) on a Beckmann DU₂ spectrophotometer and pmr spectra in (CDCl₃) on a Varian A60 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

The glyoxalate (2): To a suspension of sodium methoxide (0.54 g) in dry pyridine (50 ml) in an atmosphere of nitrogen, was added a solution of dimethyl oxalate (1.18 g) in dry pyridine (25 ml). Then 3 β -acetoxyandrost-5-en-17-one (0.50 g) in dry pyridine (30 ml) was added dropwise to the above solution at room temperature and the reaction mixture was stirred for 5 h. It was then diluted with ice-cold water and acidified with dilute HCl. The glyoxalate compound separated as white precipitate, was recrystallised from methanol-acetic acid, (65%); it was tlc homogeneous in petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 2), m.p. 170° (Found: C, 69.2, H, 7.6; O, 22.7. C₂₄H₃₂O₆ requires: C, 69.3; H, 7.7; O, 23.0%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400 (OH associated) and 1 710 cm⁻¹ (keto group at C₁₇ and also C=O of carbomethoxy); $\lambda_{\max}$ ($\epsilon_{\max}$) 215 (4.1) and 252 nm (3.8) (conjugated dioxofunction); δ 3.2 (3H, m, COOCH₃) and 2.1 (3H, s, acetoxy).

The pyrazole (3): To a solution of glyoxalate (2; 0.50 g) in acetic acid (35 ml), was added hydrazine hydrate (3 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 30 min at 170°. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and poured into ice-cold water. The white solid separated was recrystallised from methanol-acetic acid, (60%); it was tlc homogeneous in petroleum ether-benzene-acetone mixture (8 : 4 : 1), m. p. 141° (Found: C, 69.9; H, 7.7; N, 6.7; O, 15.3. C₂₄H₃₂O₄N₂ requires: C, 69.9; H, 7.8; N, 6.8; O, 15.5%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 350 (NH), 1 725 (C=O) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 8.1 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchangeable) 4.9 (1H, s, C₆-vinyllic proton), 3.5 (3H, bs, CO COOCH₃), 2.5 (2H, s, methylene at C₁₅) and 2.05 (3H, s, acetoxy).

The phenylpyrazole (4): To a solution of the glyoxalate (2; 0.50 g) in acetic acid (25 ml), were added phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride (0.30 g) and sodium acetate (0.34 g). The mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 20 min, then concentrated by distillation under reduced pressure and poured into ice-cold water. The yellowish solid obtained was recrystallised from methanol-acetic acid, (54%), it was tlc homogeneous in benzene-acetone (8 : 1) mixture, m.p. 160° (Found : C, 73.7 ; H, 7.3 ; N, 5.7 ; O, 13.1. C₃₀H₃₆N₂O₄ requires :

C, 73.8 ; H, 7.4 ; N, 5.8 ; O, 13.0%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 720 (C=O, CO.COOCH₃), 1 600 (C=C), 1 580 (C=C aromatic) and 740 cm⁻¹ (mono-substituted aromatic ring) ; $\lambda_{\max}$ ($\epsilon_{\max}$) 240 (3.9) and 290 (2.9) (aromatic and olefinic) ; δ 7.2—7.4 (5H, m, ArH), 3.1 (3H, m, CO.COOCH₃) and 2.1 (3H, s, acetoxy).

Isoxazole (5): To a solution of the glyoxalate (2; 0.5 g) in acetic acid (25 ml), were added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.14 g) and sodium acetate (0.34 g). The mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 30 min at 170° and then allowed to cool

to room temperature. The pale yellow solid separated was recrystallised from methanol-acetic acid, (55%), it was tlc homogeneous in benzene-acetone (8 : 1) mixture, m.p. 104° (Found : C, 69.7 ; H, 7.4 ; N, 3.1 ; O, 19.3. C₂₄H₃₁NO₃ requires : C, 69.74 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 3.4 ; O, 19.36%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 580, 1 590 (unsaturation) and 1 750 cm⁻¹ (C=O of carbomethoxy) ; $\lambda_{\max}$ ($\epsilon_{\max}$) 210 nm (3.1) ; δ 3.2 (3H, s, CO.COOCH₃), 2.1 (3H, s, acetoxy) and 4.9 (1H, m, vinylic proton).

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